

**DEVELOPMENT AND EFFECTIVENESS OF MOBILE LEARNING
APPLICATION SOFTWARE WITH RESPECT TO MEANINGFUL
CORRELATION AND SUSTAINED ENGAGEMENT TO ENHANCE B.
Ed. STUDENTS LEARNING**

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Introduction

In modern era, knowledge expansion is quickly changing due to the rapid development of mobile devices. In particular, the advancement of mobile devices such as Smartphone, Smart Pad and others have increased use of them and accordingly, numerous apps in various fields are in use. Among these apps, apps for educational use are in the development stage and can be regarded as one field of infrastructure construction for the enhancement of educational quality. The use of digital technologies in higher education attracted great interest in recent years, It is a common expectation for academic staff and the administrator to investigate options to ensure the learning environment is modern, relevant capable of producing graduates with the attributes aligned with the work environment and their career expectation. Mobile-learning (m-learning) has been claimed as the future of learning. Applications (apps) are fundamental features of mobile devices and the volume and the complexity of apps continues to increase.

Review of Related Literature:

Pahade P. & et al (2019), conducted study on “**Integration of Mobile Application in Education.**” This conceptual paper analyses the comparison among different available learning apps in education field and work of other researchers in related field. This paper discusses the process of integration of meaningful apps which promotes the collaboration among student and teachers. It was prepared to show teachers and students the importance or usefulness of mobile learning apps and educational mobile multimedia and social networking, and help them build a confidence for proper integration which help to develop a conducive learning environment. The results indicated that mobile app serves as bridge between educational technology and computer science and mobile app integration was effective, efficient and multidisciplinary for education.

Klimova B. (2019) studied, “**Impact of Mobile Learning on students’ Achievement Results.**” The purpose of this pilot study is to illustrate that foreign language learning supported by a personalized smartphone app can be effective in the enhancement of university students’ performance by implementing smartphone app learning in a continuous assessment. The results reveal that foreign language learning, particularly studying and revising English vocabulary and phrases via smartphones is effective in the enhancement of university students’ performance.

Hans G. (2018) studied “**Mobile learning application and its usage among students in education.**” This research paper report on the Mobile Learning Application and its usage among students in education and academic staff at the college or institute. This Research paper finds that there are various advantages of mobile learning application like ERP software in which immediate feedback, simulations, records, study materials, and capture all the data in the system only. With a rapid development in the education sector, mobile learning has become a beneficial additive in a formal learning. Therefore should be able to understand the impact of the latest technologies used for the learning or upgrade skills. Users are satisfied with mobile learning but the app is determined by various factors, such as assertiveness of learners’ attention, and the limitation of technical function etc.

Nath H. & Das S. (2020), conducted study on “**Mobile Learning during Covid -19 Pandemic: A Critical Survey on Student’s Experience In Assam**”. This paper

discussed that mobile learning plays important role in online classes, submission of assignments, for test etc. The results indicated that mobile learning has become evolving method of teaching and learning. Most of educational institution accepted various online ways to facilitate learning experience to students.

Hirsh-Pasek et al (2015) conducted a study on, “**Putting Education in “Educational” Apps:Lessons from the Science of Learning**” Study reveals that apps designed to promote active, engaged, meaningful, and socially interactive learning—four “pillars” of learning—within the context of a supported learning goal are considered educational.

Aims Of The Study

1. To develop a mobile learning application software to enhance B. Ed. students learning.
2. To study the effectiveness of mobile learning application software to enhance B. Ed. students learning.

Objectives Of The Study

1. To study the curriculum of two years credit based choice system for the B.Ed.students.
2. To study the project based course of the B. Ed curriculum based on two years choice based credit system.
3. To develop mobile learning application software for the project based course to enhance B. Ed students learning for the two years credit based choice system.
4. To implement the mobile learning application software for the project based course to enhance B. Ed students learning for the two years credit based choice system.
5. To study the pre-test and post test scores of meaningful correlation to enhance B. Ed students Learning for the two years credit based choice system.
6. To study the pre-test and post test scores of sustained engagement to enhance B. Ed students learning for the two years credit based choice system.
7. To compare the pre-test and post test scores of meaningful correlation to enhance B. Ed students Learning for the two years credit based choice system.
8. To compare the pre-test and post test scores of sustained engagement to enhance B. Ed students learning for the two years credit based choice system

Hypothesis Of The Study

1. There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post test scores of the project based course for meaningful correlation to enhance B. Ed students learning for the two credit based choice system.
2. There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post test scores of the project based

course for sustained engagement to enhance B. Ed students learning for the two years credit based choice system.

Delimitations Of The Study

1. The present study was delimited to all project based courses of B. Ed curriculum based on two years credit based choice system only.
2. The present study was delimited to check with following variables only.
 - i) Meaningful correlation
 - ii) Sustained engagement
3. The present study was delimited to English medium B. Ed. students only.

Research Methodology

Research design

The present study was conducted by employing experimental method of research involving one group pre-test post-test research design.

Sample

B. Ed. Students from teacher training college for sample was selected through **convenient sampling**. In the present study, the sample consisted of 80 student teachers from Sir J. P. College of Education and Research, Palghar B. Ed. batch.

Tools used

For the purpose of the research, the researcher used two tools to collect information from B. Ed. Students of Mumbai University. These include researcher made tools.

- 1) Pre Test-Post Test Questionnaire
- 2) Mobile learning application software developed on the basis of project based course of credit based choice system curriculum for B. Ed. Students.

Pre Test-Post Test Questionnaire consisted 2 tool based on

- i) Meaningful correlation
- ii) Sustained engagement

Validity of tool

For the purpose of checking validity of the tool, Content validity was done from six experts.

Reliability of Tool

Reliability of tool based on pilot study data was calculated using SPSS. Reliability with Cronbach alpha, Split half reliability technique and Correlation was calculated using SPSS. Reliability of tool is as follows:

Table 1
Reliability of the tool

Sr. No.	Name of Tool	Cronbach alpha	Split half	Correlation
01	Meaningful Correlation	0.878	0.959	0.959
02	Sustained Engagement	0.834	0.951	0.908

Procedure

For the present study the researcher employed the following procedure which comprised of the following steps.

1. Researcher took permission from B. Ed College principal to collect the data from respective B. Ed college students.
2. The researcher studied the project based course of B. Ed curriculum based on two years credit based choice system.
3. The researcher prepared the mobile learning application software for student-teacher by catering to their needs in teaching learning process of project based course of B. Ed. curriculum based on two years credit based choice system.
4. A group of 80 students from first year B. Ed was selected for the study of pre-test.
5. Before the implementation, researcher conducted pre-test on group at the once the first year was ended.
6. Mobile learning application software was made available on Play Store and links was forwarded to experimental group on their mobile number.
7. Implementation of the mobile learning application software was conducted for the enhancement of project based course of second year in teaching learning process in two phases, once at the time of semester III project based course and second time was at the time of semester IV project based course.
8. The post test was conducted on same group at the completion of second year project based course and with the help of quantitative data effectiveness was checked.
9. Data was collected by the administration of the tool and followed by analysis and interpretation using appropriate statistical technique.
10. Reaction analysis was conducted with open ended questionnaire to confirm the efficiency of the mobile learning application software after data analysis.

Results

Table 2
Difference in mean scores of Pre test and Post test

Hypothesis	Variable		Mean	Standard Deviation	't' value	Level of significance	N
1	Meaningful correlation	Pre test	93.875	7.204	0.279	Non-significant	80
		Post test	95.225	8.050			
2	Sustained engagement	Pre test	75.9	6.599	0.136	Non-significant	80
		Post test	77.6	7.860			

Analysis of Open Ended Tool (Reaction Analysis)

After inferential analysis, researcher conducted an open ended questionnaire after the post test & data analysis to check the opinion of the student for the efficiency of JYOTI App in B. Ed. teaching learning process. Open ended questionnaire with 5 questions were asked using google form. Data were collected using online mode due to pandemic.

Following is the analysis of the reaction of the B. Ed students.

1) Did you use the JYOTI App while performing internship activities?

Table 3
Response distribution for using the JYOTI App while performing internship activities

Response	Yes	No	Total
No. of responses	65	0	65
Percentage	100%	0%	100

Graph 1

Response distribution for using the JYOTI App while performing internship activities in percentage

2) Did you find JYOTI App content was meaningfully correlated with project based course activities?

Table 4

Response distribution for extent of which JYOTI App content was found meaningfully correlated with project based course activities

Response	Yes	No	Total
No. of responses	65	0	65
Percentage	100%	0%	100

Graph 2

Response distribution for extent of which JYOTI App content was found meaningfully correlated with project based course activities in percentage

3) How did JYOTI App was helpful to create/maintained the interest in performing project based course activities among you?

Table 5

Response distribution for the extent of JYOTI App was helpful to create/maintained the interest in performing project based course activities among students.

	Clearly mentioned many activities	Easy access/ helpful	Effective for new concept	Proper guidance	Detailed instruction & explanation	Systematic & innovative Information	Lively learning experience (demo)	Clarified doubts like teacher	Total
No. of response	3	7	4	7	13	19	9	3	65
Percentage	5%	11%	6%	11%	20%	29%	14%	5%	100%

Graph 3

Response distribution for the extent of JYOTI App was helpful to create/maintained the interest in performing project based course activities among students in percentage

4) How did JYOTI App is different than normal teaching?

Table 6

Response distribution for uniqueness of JYOTI App than normal teaching

	Wholistic information and training about newer digital tools of teaching	Easy access & language /Digital View of all activities	Systematic presentation of information for effective teaching	Well organized & interactive	Motivates to do things creatively with interest	Clarification of concepts at any time	Information for performing PBC	Good for online study lovers	Total
No. of response	13	10	14	6	10	5	5	2	65
Percentage	20%	15%	22%	9%	15%	8%	8%	3%	100%

Graph No. 4

Response distribution for uniqueness of JYOTI App than normal teaching in percentage

5) Do you think JYOTI App is useful in B. Ed for future batches?

Table 7

Response distribution for opinion of students about usefulness of JYOTI App in B. Ed for future batches

Response	Yes	No	Total
No. of responses	65	0	65
Percentage	100%	0%	100

Graph 5

Response distribution for opinion of students about usefulness of JYOTI App in B. Ed for future batches in percentage

Conclusion and Discussion

Conclusion for hypothesis 1. There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post test scores of the project based course for meaningful correlation to enhance B. Ed students learning for the two years credit based choice system.

Discussion: No difference in pretest and post test implies that B. Ed students believed that B. Ed syllabus and JYOTI mobile app gives project based courses related content which are meaningfully correlated.

Conclusion for hypothesis 2. There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post test scores of the project based course for sustained engagement to enhance B. Ed students learning for the two years credit based choice system.

Discussion: The project based courses of B. Ed are having the activities which demand interest for learning truly. No difference in pretest and post test implies that JYOTI mobile app has features which sustained engagement among the B. Ed students while learning project based course activities as B. Ed syllabus

Conclusion for reaction analysis:

1. All the respondents used the JYOTI App while performing internship activities.
2. All the respondents' finds App content was meaningfully correlated with project based course activities.
3. JYOTI App was helpful to create/maintained the interest in performing project based course activities among B. Ed students due to systematic and innovative information with detailed instructions which are very easy to access for learning new concepts effectively.
4. JYOTI App is different than normal teaching by giving wholistic information and training about newer digital tools of teaching for performing project based course with easy language, easy access with digital view of all activities, clarification of concepts at any time.
5. All the respondents thinks that JYOTI App is useful in B. Ed for future batches.

Discussion:

All the respondents finds that JYOTI App was meaningfully correlated and engages them continuously in learning project based courses/ internship activities.

Overall Discussion:

As study was limited to project based courses of B. Ed syllabus, which consist all activities which demands aspects like meaningful correlation, sustained engagement. The

efficiency of Jyoti mobile application was assessed on the same parameter wherein it was observed that there is no statistical difference in learning project based courses of first year with B. Ed syllabus and learning project based courses of second year with Jyoti mobile application. This indicates that learning project based courses with B. Ed syllabus involves the teacher educator for teaching the concept of project based courses time to time. Self-learning of project based courses with Jyoti mobile application has no statistical difference with teacher teaching. But according to analysis of reaction of B. Ed students over JYOTI app, it was found that JYOTI app is helpful in enhancing meaningful correlation and sustained engagement. It also revealed that JYOTI app is different than normal teaching and it is useful app for learning project based course for future batches.

Suggestions

Suggestions to improve efficiency of Jyoti Mobile learning Application Software:

More research need to do about what student teachers love to learn in two year B. Ed course. According to data, new content can be added which can cover all practical as well as theory based aspects too.

Focus on delivering content in more easily and attractive manner like slide show or template form, Gist of topic in pictorial format, may encourage user to use app frequently. More interactive, self-assessment and challenging evaluation techniques can be incorporated for learner which engages them more.

Immediate virtual feedback feature can be introduced which motivates to involve more in task completion with enthusiasm.

References

1. **Davis, M. (2020).** Validation of the educational effectiveness of a mobile learning app to improve knowledge about MR image quality optimization and artefact reduction. *Insights into Imaging*, 9:721–730.
2. **Dhawan, S. (2020).** Online Learning: A Panacea in the Time of COVID-19 Crisis, *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 0(0):1-18.
3. **Gregory, S. & et al (2019).** A Phenomenographic Research Study of Students' Conceptions of Mobile Learning: An Example From Higher Education, *SAGE Open*: 1-17.
4. **Hans, G. (2018).** Mobile learning application and its usage among students in education. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 5(1):984-998. (ISSN-2349-5162).

5. **Hirsh-Pasek et al (2015)**. Putting Education in “Educational” Apps:Lessons from the Science of Learning. *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*, 16(1):3– 34.
6. **Jha, G. K. & et al (2021)**. Student’s Perception and Preference for Online Education in India during COVID-19 pandemic. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 3(3).
7. **Latifa, I. S. (2018)**. Analysis of Teacher’s Lesson Plan through Behavioral Objectives Theory.” *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, 82: 6-11.
8. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.569363>
9. **Klimova, B. (2019)**. Impact of Mobile Learning on Students’ Achievement Results. *Education Sciences*,9 (90):1-8.
- 10.**Nath, H. & Das, S. (2020)**. Mobile Learning During Covid -19 Pandemic: A Critical Survey On Student’s Experience In Assam. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(6)
- 11.**Pahade, P. & et al (2019)**. Integration of Mobile Application in Education. *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 06(1):1308-1314.